

140 South Dearborn Street
Suite 1100

Chicago, Illinois 60603-5285
Telephone: (312) 726-8000.

THE JOHN D. AND CATHERINE T.
MACARTHUR FOUNDATION

July 17, 1991

Mr. Christopher Vaughn
Director
Fundacion Pro Ciencia, Arte y Cultura de la
Universidad Nacional
Apartado 86
Heredia 3,000
Costa Rica

Dear Mr. Vaughn:

The John D. and Catherine T. MacArthur Foundation has approved a three-year grant of \$195,000 to the Fundacion Pro Ciencia Arte y Cultura de la Universidad Nacional in support of its Regional Program in Wildlife Management for Mesoamerica and the Caribbean. The grant funds will be used as described in the proposal to the Foundation (undated) and the budget (hereinafter called the "approved budget") submitted to the Foundation with Mr. Jorge Fallas' letter dated July 9, 1991.

Following receipt of a countersigned copy of this agreement \$75,000 of this grant will be paid in 1991. Payments of \$65,000 and \$55,000 in 1992, and 1993 respectively, will be contingent upon review of reports, satisfactory to the Foundation, of your organization's use of grant funds paid in the year preceding each such scheduled payment.

These terms apply to your organization's use of the Foundation's grant:

Under United States law, Foundation grant funds, and income earned thereon, may be expended only for charitable, religious, scientific, literary or educational purposes. This grant is made only for the purposes stated in this letter, and it is understood that these grant funds will be used for such purposes substantially in accordance with the approved budget. It is also understood that no substantial variances, including the timing of expenditures, will be made from the approved budget without the Foundation's prior approval in writing.

The Foundation encourages, whenever feasible, the deposit of grant funds in an interest-bearing account. Any grant funds, and income earned thereon, not expended or committed for the purposes of the grant will be returned to the Foundation.

Two copies of any publications produced or disseminated wholly or in part with these funds will be furnished to the Foundation. Such publications should include an appropriate acknowledgement of the support from the Foundation.

Foundation grant funds may not be used by your organization to carry on propaganda, or otherwise to attempt to influence any legislation, within the meaning of Section 4945 of the Internal Revenue Code and the Treasury Regulations thereunder. By countersigning this agreement your organization confirms that none of the grant funds will be used for such purposes.

A written report signed by an appropriate officer of your organization is to be furnished to the Foundation, to the attention of Dr. Dan M. Martin, Director, World Environment and Resources Program, following the close of each of your fiscal years, in which you receive or expend any portion of the grant funds until the grant funds are expended in full. (According to our records your fiscal year ends December 31.) Reports are due no later than February 28 of 1992, 1993 and 1994.

These reports should contain a financial statement and a narrative account of what was accomplished by the expenditure of funds, including a description of progress made toward achieving the goals of the grant. The financial statement should reflect expenditures of the grant funds, and any income earned thereon, according to the categories of the approved budget, as of the end of the period covered by the report.

The Foundation may monitor and conduct an evaluation of operations under this grant, which may include a visit from Foundation personnel to observe your organization's program, discuss the program with your organization's personnel, and review financial and other records and materials connected with the activities financed by this grant.

The Foundation will include information on this grant in its periodic public reports and may also refer to the grant in a press release. If you wish to make a public announcement, please consult with the Foundation before doing so.

Your organization has previously submitted to the Foundation a statement providing answers to and accompanying documentation for the form entitled "Information Requested of Foreign Grantee Organizations Which Do Not Have 501(c)(3) and 509(a) Determination

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Letters From The U. S. Internal Revenue Service". It is understood that by countersigning this letter your organization confirms that there have been no material changes in such statement or documentation and that you will inform the Foundation of any material changes in such statement or documentation in the future.

On behalf of the Foundation, may I extend every good wish for the success of this endeavor.

Sincerely,

Victor Rabinowitch
Vice President for Programs

VR/ek2354

Enclosures

ACCEPTED AND AGREED:

(Grantee)

By: UNIVERSIDAD NACIONAL

Title: Rector

Date: August 8th, 1991

Payment check should be directed to:

FUNDACION PRO CIENCIA, ARTE Y CULTURA DE LA UNIVERSIDAD NACIONAL
(name)

(title)

Universidad Nacional, Apartado 86, 3000 Heredia, Costa Rica
(address)

Grant # 9113019A
Environment